

1 **FKBP prolyl isomerases are therapeutic targets in lung metastatic breast cancer.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 Fkbp proteins are prolyl isomerases with cyclophilin-like function and important for metabolic pathways like
7 mTOR. We describe here identification of Fkbp1a and Fkbp3 as over-expressed therapeutic targets in
8 lung metastatic breast cancer.

9 Citations

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